

Trusted digital repositories: audit and certification

As discussed in the chapter on Access and Reuse, trust is an important aspect of the relationship between repositories and their stakeholders – especially, data producers and consumers. As digital assets are easily manipulated and threatened by loss or obsolescence, preserving their authenticity and integrity is a responsible task. Stakeholders (including funders) have to be convinced that the archive or repository is up to the task. One answer to this problem is for repositories to seek “external acknowledgement” by subjecting their workflows and procedures to external review based on accepted standards.

Audit and certification

After the first publication of the OAIS Reference Model in 2002, archives and repositories began describing themselves as “OAIS-compliant” with the intention of demonstrating that they could be trusted with the preservation and dissemination of digital assets. However, in the early days of digital preservation, no metrics existed to measure compliance with OAIS or, generally, trustworthiness of digital repositories. In response to this problem, over the years various checklists and criteria catalogs were developed, to be used in assessing the trustworthiness of digital archives and to ultimately serve the purpose of certification. These include the following:

- Trusted Digital Repositories: Attributes and Responsibilities. An RLG-OCLC Report (RLG, 2002)
- DRAMBORA: Digital Repository Audit Method Based on Risk Assessment (DCC & DPE, 2007)
- Trustworthy Repositories Audit & Certification: Criteria and Checklist (OCLC & CRL, 2007)
- nestor criteria. Catalogue of Criteria for Trusted Digital Repositories. Version 2 (nestor, 2009)
- Data Seal of Approval. Quality Guidelines for Digital Research Data (2009, 2013)
- Audit and Certification of Trustworthy Digital Repositories. Recommended Practice (CCSDS, 2011)
- DIN 31644: Criteria for trustworthy digital archives (2012)
- ISO 16363: Audit and certification of trustworthy digital repositories (2012).

European Framework for Audit and Certification

In an effort to coordinate approaches to audit and certification of digital repositories, in 2010 a memorandum was signed to create a “European Framework for Audit and Certification of Digital Repositories” (<http://www.trusteddigitalrepository.eu/>). The framework integrates three standards: the Data Seal of Approval (DSA, 2009 + 2013), DIN 31644 (2012), and ISO 16363 (2012). It takes a tiered approach by defining three levels of certification, thereby enabling archives to choose a certification procedure suitable to their size, objectives, and available resources.

Basic Certification is acquired through the DSA, which consists of a set of 16 guidelines relating to data producers, repositories, and users. To obtain the DSA, repositories carry out a self-assessment using the guidelines. The assessment and the documentation provided is reviewed by a member of the DSA board.

Extended Certification is granted to repositories which have obtained the DSA and successfully carried out an externally reviewed self-assessment based on either ISO 16363 or DIN 31644. The ISO standard “Audit and certification of trustworthy digital repositories” consists of more than 80 criteria addressing the following areas:

- “organizational infrastructure – which addresses the repository organisation can provide
- digital object management – which addresses the fundamentals of digital preservation, following the OAIS concepts
- infrastructure and security risk management – addressing security aspects. . .”
(<http://www.iso16363.org/standards/iso-16363/>).

The DIN standard, which derives from the nestor Catalogue of Criteria for Trusted Digital Repositories and can be used to obtain the nestor Seal (nestor, 2013), comprises of 34 criteria covering the same areas as the ISO standard.

Formal Certification, the highest level in the European Framework, requires that repositories obtain the DSA and submit to a full external audit in accordance with either ISO or DIN.

Recommended introductory resources

The presentations of the DASISH workshop on trust and certification, held in October 2014, give an overview of the standards comprising the European Framework and present case studies from different organizations who have obtained the DSA or are preparing for the nestor Seal. See <http://dasish.eu/dasishevents/wstrustcertification/prelprogramme/>.

On his blog, David Rosenthal gives an overview of a recent audit against Trustworthy Repositories Audit & Certification: Criteria and Checklist (TRAC), which involved into ISO 16363: <http://blog.dshr.org/2014/08/trac-audit-process.html>.

Why audit?

(Self-) audits and assessments against the mentioned standards and criteria catalogs allow repositories to demonstrate their trustworthiness to stakeholders, thus fulfilling an important function in stakeholder communication. However, more importantly, they also fulfill a function relating to internal workflows and procedures as they enable repositories to critically assess these, thus helping them to spot possible gaps.

References

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